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ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNAL

Jild: 1, Son: 02 (2024)

ISSN: XXXX-XXXX

Inflation and Curriculum Implementation in Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD), Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper assessed the impact of inflation on curriculum implementation in Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD), Nigeria. The paper adopted secondary data. The secondary data were collected from online publications and print resources. The paper established that inflation has led to increment in the operational cost, instructional resources and suspension of infrastructure facilities development and has affected teachers' job performance in the various Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) across the country. Based on this findings, the paper recommends that government should increase the salaries of teachers. Government should increase the budgetary allocation of Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) to allow managers and administrators complete ongoing infrastructure facilities. Government should subsidize the cost of instructional resource for all Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) schools in Nigeria.

Keywords: Curriculum, Curriculum Implementation, Inflation.

Introduction

The Nigerian secondary school also known as Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) is the education children receive after a successful completion of nine years of Basic Education and passing the Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) and Junior Arabic and Islamic Studies Certificate Examination (JAISCE). It includes: (i) senior secondary education, (ii) higher school; and (iii) continuing education given in Vocational Enterprise Institutions (VEIs) to either Basic Education graduates who are not proceeding to Senior Secondary Schools, or Senior Secondary graduates that are not proceeding to the tertiary level, as a means of preparing them for the world of work, wealth creation and entrepreneurship (National policy on education 2014).

The objectives of Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) according to (National policy on education 2014) are to: a. provide holders of the Basic Education Certificate and Junior Arabic and Islamic Studies Certificate with opportunity for education of a higher level, irrespective of gender, social status, religious or ethnic background; b. offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, disposition, opportunities and future roles; c. provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades; d. provide entrepreneurial, technical and vocational job-specific skills for self-reliance, and for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development; e. develop and promote Nigerian languages, art and culture in the context of world's cultural heritage; f. inspire students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence; g. foster patriotism, national unity and security education with emphasis on the common ties in spite of our diversity; and h. raise morally upright and well-adjusted individuals who can think independently and rationally, respect the views and feelings of others and appreciate the dignity of labour. (National policy on education 2014).

Inflation appear to be affecting development of Education in Nigeria. The rate at which inflation is going is posing danger to management of education. Udi (2024) reported that Nigeria's inflation rate increased to 33.2% for the month of March 2024 according to the latest data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). This represents 1.5% point increase from the 31.7% recorded in February 2024. The increase in the inflation rate in March was slower compared to the 1.80% increase recorded in February 2024. On a year-on-year basis, the headline inflation rate increased by 11.16% from 22.04% in March 2023. Additionally, the headline inflation rate for March 2024 was 3.02%, a decrease of 0.10% from February 2024, when it was 3.12%. In March 2024, the food inflation rate reached 40.01% year-on-year, marking an increase of 15.56 percentage points from 24.45% in March 2023. This surge in food inflation can be attributed to rising prices for items such as garri, millet, and akpu uncooked fermented (all part of the Bread and Cereals category), as well as yam tuber, water yam, and others. The inflation did not only affects food prices, it also affects operational cost of both private and public institutions which include education.

Inflation is one of the most frequently used terms in economic discussions, yet the concept is variously misconstrued. There are various schools of thought on inflation, but there is a consensus among economists that inflation is a continuous rise in the prices. Simply put, inflation depicts an economic situation where there is a general rise in the prices of goods and services, continuously. It could be defined as 'a continuing rise in prices as measured by an index such as the consumer price index (CPI) or by the implicit price deflator for Gross National Product (GNP)'. Inflation is frequently described as a state where "too much money is chasing too few goods". When there is inflation, the currency loses purchasing power. The purchasing power of a given amount of naira will be smaller over time when there is inflation in the economy. For instance, assuming that N10.00 can purchase 10 shirts in the current period, if the price of shirts double in the next period, the same N10.00 can only afford 5 shirts (Obiakor 2021). Based on this, it

is import to examine the impact of inflation on curriculum implementation in Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD), Nigeria.

Conceptual Terms

Curriculum Implementation

Curriculum implementation is the actual engagement of learners with planned learning opportunities (Nuhu, 2024). Curriculum implementation is the practical execution of planned documents of instruction in the schools (Akin-Ibidiran, Ogunode, & Ibidiran, 2022). Curriculum implementation according to Ivowi (2004) involves a number of activities culminating in translating curriculum documents into classroom practice. It involves translation of theory into practice or proposal into action. This is achieved when the teacher is handed the curriculum and ends when the learners have been exposed to the learning experiences prescribed in the document. There are intermediate steps which includes verbal and non-verbal exposition, practical work in the laboratories, interactions, workshops, field work, teacher – student interactions, student-materials interactions and the evaluation and feedback.

Curriculum implementation as the various steps involved in achieving the derived curriculum objectives of educational programs. Curriculum implementation is the act of executing a planned curriculum document into the practical curriculum (Ekpo & Oka, 2009). Curriculum implementation is the task of translating the curriculum document into the operating curriculum by the combined efforts of the students, teachers and others concerned. That is, curriculum implementation demands concerted efforts of end-users of the curriculum for its effective implementation at all levels to achieve the desired goals (Mkpa, 2007). Okoro, (2010), noted that Curriculum implementation makes teachers to prepare lesson notes, use reinforcement and motivational strategies, classroom control and creation of friendly relationship, application of theories and principles of learning, effective use of evaluation techniques and adequate consideration of learner’s cognitive styles. This facilitates resolution of instructional challenges as well as achievement of overall goals of education, which is the vision of the 21st century.

Curriculum implementation is the transition of the objectives of the curriculum from paper to practice. That is, only effective curriculum implementation ensures the achievement of the objectives for which the curriculum was designed to attain (Okebukola, 2004). Ejike, & Ejike (2018), maintained that curriculum implementation fosters curriculum evaluation and this guides the learning outcomes. The major implementers of the curriculum are the teachers. They set up learning opportunities aimed at enabling learners to acquire the desired knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values through the adoption of appropriate teaching methods and materials to guide students’ learning. The curriculum planned and developed is implemented through the medium of instruction. This is why curriculum implementation is seen as the daily activities of school management and classroom teachers in the pursuit of the achievement of the objectives of the school curriculum, all in a bid to realize the national philosophy of education. Curriculum implementation appear to be affected by factors like inflation.

Inflation

Inflation as a sustained increase in the general price level of goods and services in an economic over a period of time. To break it down; it means that the value of money decreases over time, causing the prices of things to go up the roof. Basically, the same amount of money can buy fewer goods and services than usual (Pans pressui 2024). Inflation which is defined as the sustained increase in the general price level of goods and services in an economy though can be beneficial to some areas of the economy, like stimulating economic growth, it can also cause some serious problems, especially when it comes to the cost of feeding, acquiring teaching and learning materials, tuition fees, salaries of teachers and transportation costs of both students and teachers (Ahmed, & Tochukwu, 2024).

Ogunode, Olowonefe and Olumodeji (2024) defined inflation as an economic period when there are much money in circulation that can only buy few goods and services. Inflation occurs when the purchasing power of money is lost or low to buy what it used to normally buy before. It is when large sum of money is chasing only few goods and services during a given time. Inflation is defined by Ogunode and Ukozor (2023) as the continuous rise in the prices of goods and services over the period of time. Inflation is the continuous fall in the purchasing value of money, in that, more money chases fewer goods and services, which adversely affects negatively on the economy and reduces the standard of living of the population (Ogbebor, Oguntodu, & Oyinloye, 2020).

Impact of Inflation on Curriculum Implementation of Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD), Nigeria

There are many impacts of inflation on curriculum implementation in Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria. Some of the impacts include; increment in the operational cost, instructional resources and suspension of infrastructure facilities development and has affected teachers' job performance in the various Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) across the country.

Increment in the operational cost

Inflation in Nigeria has pushed the prices of goods and services up and this directly affected the operation of public and private institutions especially the educational institutions which include Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria. Research by Muhammed (2020) and Adeyemi (2022) revealed that inflation has led to high operational cost of running educational institutions. Ogunode, Cletus, & Tswenji (2024) observed during inflation, managers of schools due to a shortage of funds available to schools decided to reduce procurement of all needed educational resources and only purchase a few as a result inflation increases the operational cost of the schools. This decision of not buying the required and adequate teaching and learning resources affects the quality of education because education can be likened to a system in that all resources must be provided with the right qualities and deployed. The failure to do this will affect the quality of education. Inflation affects the prices of educational resources that are used for running education facilities and this also militated against effective implementation of schools curriculum and other relative programmes. Also, Ogunode, Eze, and Olumodeji (2024) established that inflation affected implementation of teaching programme, research programme and community service programme in Nigerian universities.

Instructional resources

The inflation in Nigeria has led to increases in the general prices of instructional resources. Instructional materials are educational resources assembled by the teachers to implement teaching programmes in the classroom. Instructional materials are special educational resources that aid the teachers to deliver the lesson (Ogunode, and Josiah, 2023). Instructional materials as objects or devices that assist teachers to present their lessons logically and sequentially to the learners (Isola (2010). Ogunode, et al (2023) observed that instructional materials are used in all forms of educational institutions. The resources are influencing the implementation of teaching, research and community service in the various tertiary institutions. In secondary schools, instructional materials are supporting teaching and learning. Teachers in educational institutions teach well with the deployment of instructional materials. Instructional materials serve as a channel between the teacher and the students in delivering instructions. Study by Nwankwo (2018) disclosed that inflation has a negative impact on the availability of educational resources, such as classroom space and textbooks. Adegoke, (2011) did a study and found out that most of the respondents (66.7%) reported that inflation has led to an increase in the cost of basic education. Inflation has led to high cost of instructional resource which directly affected curriculum implementation (Ogunode, Eze, &

Olumodeji, 2024; Giami, 2023). Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in 2018 found out that the rising cost of tuition, books, and other educational expenses can place a financial burden on students and their families, making it difficult for them to afford an education. The report also found that higher inflation rates can lead to a decrease in the availability of scholarships and other financial aid, which can further reduce enrollment. Inflation can hamper education development because it makes all educational resources unreachable to school managers, students and parents and this affects curriculum implementation in schools.

Suspension of infrastructure facilities development

Inflation in Nigeria has affected infrastructure facilities projects development and completion in Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) across the country. Infrastructural facilities are those resources, made of materials that help any institution carry out service delivery. Infrastructure facilities, in particular, are those found in postsecondary institutions that support the implementation of community services, teaching, and research. Educational facilities are described as nonhuman and non-financial resources that include moveable and immovable things that improve teaching and learning by (Ogunode, & Agwor 2021; Ogunode, & Jegede, 2021; Odey, 2018 & Abdulkareem 2000). Inflation is responsible for the increment in the prices of building materials and other resources which has led to suspension of school infrastructure facilities projects. Inflation in Nigeria has led to a review of some major contracts awarded for the building of facilities in some basic schools across the country. Contractors handling various infrastructure facilities projects in some Basic schools in Nigeria have called for a review of the contract due to the high rate of inflation that has pushed up the prices of human and materials resources needed to complete the projects assigned and planned. Peter (2022) asserted that due to the high cost of building materials in Nigeria, many contractors managing projects in various educational institutions across the country are calling for a review of contract agreements because initial agreements on the contracts are no longer visible and implementable. Inflation has led to abandoned projects in schools. Mac-Barango (2017) established that inflation, bankruptcy of contractors, inadequate funding, inadequate planning, variation of project scope, faulty design, delay, and quackery are factors responsible for projects“ as factors responsible for projects abandonment in Nigeria. Also, Nwanekezie, and Nwanguma, (2019) confirmed that the causes of abandoned projects and found that inflation, wrong estimates, inadequate planning, poor risk management and inadequate finance are the significant factors causing the abandonment of building projects in Nigeria. Shortage of infrastructure facilities affected effective implementation of curriculum in schools.

Teachers' job performance

The teachers' job performance in most Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria appear to be affected by the high rate of inflation. Teachers' job performance according to Zaifada, Olowonefa, Ogunode (2023) is the degree to which teachers execute their official responsibilities in the school. Teachers' job performance is the capacity to effectively inculcate the three domains such as cognitive, psychomotor and affective in the learners. The teacher is a professional individual saddled with the responsibilities of curriculum implementation in the schools. Whenever the teacher' is unstable, it affects it productivities. Inflation have been linked to mental health problems. Omoru (2021) observed that most teachers in the schools now find it very hard to concentrate and often times now sleep off spasmodically in class. What is majorly responsible for this is insomnia that is occasioned by fatigue. This is as a result of too much thinking now usually associated with the economic reality in our dear country. Our teachers are worse hit and this now affects their total concentration. Due to hardship and inflation most teachers now have insomnia. Insomnia is difficulty falling asleep or staying asleep, even when a person has

the chance to do so. People with insomnia can feel dissatisfied with their sleep and experience usually symptoms such as low energy, difficulty in concentrating, decreased performance in school and general fatigue (Omoru 2021). This directly and indirectly affects productivities of lecturers in tertiary institutions. The impact of inflation and standard of living on teacher's job performance and discovered that inflation and standard of living have negative impacts on teachers' job performance among teachers in the study area and living cost (Ogunode, & Agbade, 2023; Giami, 2023). Also, inflation according to Gagarawa, and Mehrotra (2017) erodes teachers income, increased their expenditures subjecting them to receiving loans with high interest, forcing the teachers to take an extra income generating works in an attempt to maintain their normal life, these consequently undermine their living standard.

Inflation also affected living standard of teachers in schools. Akpomi, Singer, and Isaac, (2018); Organization for Economic Co- operation and Development (OECD) OECD 2016) and according to Edufund (2024) noted that the purchasing power gradually decreases, the value of goods increases, and ultimately the real value of the currency is at a loss. Inflation thus decreases the standard of living, and parents belonging to lower and middle-income groups become unable to bear the cost of educating their children as the monthly allowance that they pay to their kids doesn't make up for the price hikes and lecturers cannot afford to meet up with their academic financial demand such as publishing paper, traveling for conferences and buying instructional resources to support implementation of teaching in the classes. Some lecturers and teachers cannot afford coming to classes as they use to do before and this affected implementation of teaching programme and curriculum implementation.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper examined the impact of inflation on curriculum implementation in Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD), Nigeria. The paper established that inflation has led to increment in the operational cost, instructional resources and suspension of infrastructure facilities development and has affected teachers' job performance in the various Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) across the country.

Based on this findings, the paper recommends that government should increase the salaries of teachers. Government should increase the budgetary allocation of Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) to allow managers and administrators complete ongoing infrastructure facilities. Government should subsidize the cost of instructional resource for all Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) schools in Nigeria.

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